

A Study on the Contribution of Social Media on Public Awareness of Domestic Violence: A Case Study of the University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

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Abstract

This study investigates the contribution of social media to public awareness of domestic violence, with a specific focus on students of the Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Maiduguri. It identifies how social media platforms serve as tools for educating the public, amplifying voices, and promoting behavioural change interventions. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 120 students using online questionnaires. The findings reveal that students are aware of the role social media plays in disseminating information about domestic violence. Respondents identified social media as valuable in providing support networks, raising awareness, and creating safe spaces for survivors. Facebook was seen as the most effective platform for awareness. The study concludes that social media is a powerful tool in preventing and responding to domestic violence by enabling communication, raising public consciousness, and supporting advocacy efforts. It recommends strengthening education on social media use for awareness creation among communication students and integrating behavioural change content into online campaigns.

Keywords: Social media, domestic violence, awareness creation, Facebook, behavioural change intervention, University of Maiduguri, public communication

Introduction

The media is an indispensable agent of development in any nation given their invaluable contribution to raising the consciousness of society, and guiding the public toward change. Information is the basis for effecting change as well as tackling the consequence of change (Agudoso & Ikegbunam, 2020). The media is believed to be the most powerful instrument that can

influence values, beliefs, attitudes, thoughts, and behaviours; sometimes consciously and at other times unconsciously, reinforce negatively personal, societal, and cultural precepts regarding any form of violence (Aririguzoh, 2015). That is why the media has become a very strong medium for creating awareness on domestic violence.

Domestic violence refers to any form of abuse or violence that occurs within a domestic relationship, such as between spouses, partners, family members, or roommates. It takes many forms, including physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, and financial abuse (Dryden-Edwards, 2022). Domestic violence can have severe and lasting effects on the health and well-being of those who experience it, and it is a serious problem that affects people of all genders, ages, and all kinds of background (Rivara, Adhia, Lyons, and Massey, 2019). Some common forms of domestic violence include but not limited to hitting, slapping, pushing, forcing or coercing someone into sexual acts, verbal abuse, manipulation, gaslighting, controlling access to money or resources, or preventing someone from working (Arizona Coalition, 2023). Victims of domestic violence may experience a wide range of physical and emotional effects, including injuries, trauma, depression, and anxiety (Arizona Coalition, 2023).

Globally, the rate at which domestic violence is perpetrated is high. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2020), reported that 81,000 women and girls were killed, and around 47,000 of them died at the hands of an intimate partner or a family member. This is an average of one death every 11 minutes.

World Health Organization (2021) identified in a study, that one in four young women (aged 15-24 years), who have been in a relationship, have experienced violence by an intimate partner. A recent study found that 22% of women in Western Europe experienced intimate partner violence, rising to 32% in North America (Statista, 2023). Meanwhile in the United States, an estimated 10 million people experience domestic violence every year, and about 20 people every minute (UN Women, 2023).

In Nigeria, domestic violence is prevalent. There are series of domestic violence stories all over the country, ranging from wives being murdered by their husbands, unmarried ladies murdered by a rejected lover, and other forms of inhuman treatment (Ubong, 2018). Many families, especially women, suffer chemical and acid attacks by their spouses or partners, which result in excruciating pain or disfigurement and occasionally even result in the victims' deaths (Baba and Murray, 2017). A Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey report (2018), disclosed that on average, 14 per cent of women who were surveyed have experienced physical violence. However, the Nigerian government has taken steps to address domestic violence, including enacting laws such as the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) which was signed into law in 2015, and it criminalizes all forms of violence against persons and provides for the protection and support of victims (Oluremi, 2015).

Notable ways to address domestic violence can include leveraging on the improvements in information and communication technology, particularly social media that

allow for self-publishing, and has made it possible for victims, particularly women, to express what they are going through in texts, photos, and videos in order to elicit public condemnation, criticism and, consequently, receive the desired judgment (Philip, 2016). Thus, social media can be a valuable tool for reporting domestic violence, as it allows individuals to share their experiences and raise awareness about the issue. Many survivors of domestic violence may not feel comfortable reporting the abuse to authorities or seeking help in person, but social media can provide a way for them to speak out anonymously and connect with others who have gone through similar experiences (Philip, 2016). Also, the availability of behavioral change interventions and response to domestic violence, which can be incorporated in social media awareness campaigns, can be used in the fight against domestic violence. Behavioral change interventions are coordinated sets of activities designed to change specified behaviours of domestic violence. Via social media, awareness on certain Behavioral change interventions on domestic violence, will help prevent the escalation of domestic violence in the community.

Available studies on the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic abuse (see Rivara, Adhia, Lyons, and Massey, 2019; Isaac, 2023; Ifeanyi and Hannah, 2023; Ibid, 2005; Eze-Anaba 2006; and Okoli and Irinze, 2018) have been able to identify why incidents of domestic violence tend to go unreported, with reasons such as respect for tradition, lack of awareness and understanding of what constitutes domestic violence and lack of knowledge of rights.

These studies have identified that the use of social media can be a valuable tool for public awareness on domestic violence, and educating the public on their human rights. There are studies that have concentrated on certain social media platforms. For example, Isaac (2023), found out that twitter is the social media platforms preferably utilized in raising awareness on domestic violence. While, Okoli and Irinze (2018), found out that Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube can serve as the voice for voicing out issues of domestic violence. However, this study will focus on Facebook, as it is the most popular social media platform (Shopify, 2024), to examine the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic abuse, a case study in the university of Maiduguri.

Statement of the Problem

Numerous interventions have been deployed to address the persistent domestic violence, particularly against women, in Nigeria and elsewhere. These efforts don't seem to have done enough to stop the threat. These interventions, among others, include but are not limited to advocacy, campaigns, education, legal rulings, and outright punishment. Meanwhile, advancement in information and communication technology particularly social media has come to offer ways to address domestic violence, and even create awareness on domestic violence. Social media offer self-publishing opportunity which can enable victims of domestic violence especially women to share their stories in texts, photos and video to express what they are experiencing to arouse public condemnation, criticism and by extension getting the desire judgement.

There is a large body of research on the role of social media in raising awareness about domestic abuse in Nigeria (see Rivara, Adhia, Lyons, and Massey, 2019; Isaac, 2023; Ifeanyi and Hannah, 2023; Ibid, 2005; Eze-Anaba 2006; and Okoli and Irinze, 2018). This research found that using social media can be an effective technique for raising public awareness about domestic violence and educating people about their human rights. However, existing scholarly work on the impact of social media in raising awareness of domestic abuse in Nigeria is limited in the northern region. Also, there are available case studies within Nigeria on role of social media in creating awareness on domestic violence, but none has been conducted within the university of Maiduguri, faculty of social sciences. It is against this background that this study is on the thrust to examine the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, a case study of the university of Maiduguri.

Objectives of the Study

The research is on the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, a case study of the university of Maiduguri. The objectives of the study are;

1. to ascertain students' knowledge on social media as a tool of creating awareness on domestic violence.
2. to ascertain how social media can serve as a voice for domestic violence victims.
3. to ascertain the role of social media and behavioural change intervention to preventing and responding to domestic violence.

Literature Review

Social Media and Awareness Creation on Domestic Violence

Domestic violence has been described by UNFPA (2022) as one of the most common human rights violations worldwide, and Nigeria is no exception. Domestic violence is common in Nigeria, with no effective measures in place to curb it. Instead of denouncing the perpetrator of such acts, a culture of silence increases the stigma connected to the victim (Aihie, 2009). This can be said to be one of the reasons domestic violence occurs frequently in Nigeria.

Obi and Ozumba (2007) conducted study on the causes of domestic violence in Nigeria and found that 70% of respondents had experienced violence in their homes, with 92% of the victims being female partners and the remaining 8% being male. This demonstrates the widespread prevalence of domestic violence in the country. The subject of how domestic violence might be addressed, lessened, or eliminated is open for dispute. While opinions have focused on sanctions for offenders, there is also a need to raise awareness about domestic violence, as a lack of understanding about domestic violence is one of the causes of domestic violence.

The importance of information and communication technology (ICT) cannot be underestimated. According to Mirani, Pannu, and Malhotra (2014), new ICTs have emerged as effective tools for social participation. It is critical in forming social movements, generating awareness, and eventually giving rise to a voice that sets the

groundwork. Social media has revolutionized the way knowledge is shared around the world (Shirky, 2011). Furthermore, its widespread and exceptional use constitute critical opportunities to bring equity and rights problems to the center of policymaking and media attention (Loiseau & Nowacka, 2015). Hashtags tend to spring up now and then to address one issue related to domestic violence. This is often used as a medium to get people involved in the discussion and possibly proffers solutions to the problem.

Shirky (2011), Liou (2013), and Loiseau & Nowacka (2015) have all investigated how social media can be used to raise awareness and mobilize people, and they discovered that social media tools can help domestic violence victims share their experiences with other victims, creating a space for them to exchange knowledge and information about their rights, legal processes, and social services. In fact, Vardhan (2017) posits that social media has provided an opportunity for victims of domestic violence to have their voices heard. Furthermore, Smith (2014) stated that social media, particularly Facebook, is one of the most powerful channels for promoting violence-related concerns globally.

Social Media as a Voice for Domestic Violence Victims

Domestic violence affects individuals of all ages and has the potential to cause severe damages. Sometimes victims have been compelled to spend extended periods in isolation with their abusers, and the number of such victims continues to rise (Wong et al., 2021). Victims of domestic violence may struggle to escape or seek help for a variety

of reasons. However, there are numerous ways to help, including personalized shelter-housing approaches, education programmes, evacuation plans, rules and regulations, and more technologically based mental health therapies (Dike & Babarinde, 2013). Many domestic violence victims have turned to social media because it allows them to communicate their difficulties, connect with others, and seek help from those who understand their predicament (Malathesh, Das, and Chatterjee, 2020).

Social media offers victims access to an abundance of internet resources that they can utilise without worrying about their abusers finding out. Some of these resources as highlighted by Subramani and O'Connor (2018) in their study, includes Reddit, which is a good place for domestic abuse victims to turn for assistance. Here domestic violence counselors can meet victims and offer aids to the victims in building safety techniques and refer them to other resources. They added that even social media sites such as Snapchat provide refuge services to those fleeing abusive relationships. User-to-user interactions are made possible by Snapchat, which allow users send one another brief messages in text dialogues, videos, or photographs. Victims of domestic violence may use this to provide evidence anonymously or contact out for assistance. Also, Instagram's new "Vanish Mode" enables users to exchange messages without leaving a trace of the conversation. This implies that everything discussed between users is erased from the internet when they leave their inboxes.

Victims of domestic violence can use the internet and social media to express themselves. Those who believe they cannot ask for aid in person frequently have more freedom to do so on the internet. Certain websites are designed so that victims can easily navigate away from the page, which is especially useful for people who live or share a computer with their abusers (Bashir and Bhat, 2017). One important resource is the National Domestic Abuse Hotline's website. Their portal includes a function that allow users to click a red X in the corner of their screens, which will take them safely to Google's search page if they believe their abuser is approaching or watching them. Clicking the red X, which remains fixed in place on the screen for easy access, will also delete the page from their browser history, adding another layer of security and safety to the process of requesting assistance (Bashir and Bhat, 2017).

Social media, Behavioural Change Interventions, and Domestic Violence

Behaviour change interventions are coordinated sets of activities designed to change specified behavior patterns (Adebayo, 2013). In the context of this research, behavior change interventions are coordinated sets of activities designed to change domestic violence and related behavior patterns. The need for more effective behavior-change interventions in Nigeria cannot be overstated. Proven tools used in other countries can be applied and tailored to the local circumstances. All Nigerians must be protected from domestic violence by legislation that provide specific rules addressing domestic violence

(Adeboyo, 2011). Access to services is critical for averting difficulties, as are support services such as counseling, helplines, shelters, and resources. In reality, extensive awareness efforts, particularly those utilizing social media, are critical for disseminating domestic violence information and education in order to help victims destigmatize themselves and change their habits.

The social media space can indeed be an avenue for behavioral change intervention in respect to domestic violence. This can lead to change in behaviours of perpetrators, and a way forward for victims and survivors. Social media platforms can be sites of resistance for challenging domestic violent culture, include stigmatization, and behaviours (Blanchard, 2011). Social media presents opportunities to move beyond individual-level efforts to engage wider communities in domestic violence prevention, through widespread awareness campaigns (Wilson and Murby, 2010). These campaigns will not only inform people on domestic violence, it will inform them of the dangers, ills, consequences, prevention, response, among others, that will help change narratives surrounding domestic violence, behaviours, and provide the needed information.

Social media awareness campaigns on domestic violence are essential for providing information and education to help destigmatize victims of domestic violence and to help prevent the occurrence of domestic violence, by providing the community with information on domestic violence and its ills (Gillin 2009). In addition to social media awareness initiatives, support services such as counseling, hotlines,

shelters, and resources are required. The government can successfully use existing community structures to combat domestic violence. In rural places, empowering village heads and community chiefs to enact laws making domestic violence illegal might be a big step (Harfoush 2009). Healthcare personnel should also be educated to recognize indicators of domestic violence, such as physical injuries, psychological distress, or behavioral changes (Sikken, 2015). Health care personnel must create a safe, nonjudgmental environment in which victims can receive emotional support and understanding, encouraging them to relate their stories without fear.

Empirical Review of Related Literatures

The rate at which domestic violence continues to thrive is alarming, that is why there is need to create awareness on the menace. Isaac (2023) conducted a study on the role of social media in mitigating domestic violence against women in port Harcourt, an advocacy for policy and legal frameworks. The study was aimed at investigating how social media is used to highlight the negative effects of domestic violence. The Port Harcourt metropolitan population, comprising Port Harcourt Local Government Areas I and II and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas, served as the source for the 400-person sample size. A survey research approach was adopted and the analyses and discussions revealed a significant prevalence of domestic violence in the study area. The study recommends that the government, religious institutions, and nongovernmental organizations should take action by evolving policies and legal

instruments that will aid in lessening the threat of domestic violence against women in Nigeria.

Ifeanyi and Hannah (2023), conducted a study on the role of broadcast media in creating awareness of domestic violence in Enugu state. The study assessed the role of media in creating awareness of domestic violence in Enugu State. The study employed a Survey research design, which entails the collection of standardized information from a specific population or sample utilizing a questionnaire. The sample size for the study was 369. Stratified random sampling was employed in the study. The study concluded that the media has a special role to play in stemming the tide of domestic violence through frequent coverage, follow-up reported cases of domestic violence and proper awareness creation on the effect of domestic violence-related issues. The study recommended among others that to address effectively the issue of domestic violence in Enugu State, the media have to work harder to brace up for the task of uncovering cases of domestic violence and following up on such cases at different levels.

Okoli and Irinze (2018), conducted a study on the role of social media in domestic violence. The study examines the impact of the social media in the fight against domestic violence among women and girls in Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State. The objectives of the study include to identify the nature of domestic violence among girls in Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State, identify the role of the social media in the fight against domestic violence among women and girls Yola North

Local Government Area of Adamawa State, and find out means to enhance the role of the social media in the fight against domestic violence among women and girls Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State. The research design adopted in the study was descriptive survey design. The method of data collection was Key Informant Interview (KII). The study discovered that social media could also provide a platform for key influencers (celebrities, politicians, sports-people, women groups etc.) to publicly challenge violence. In general, to effectively address the problem of this form of domestic violence in Nigeria, the media have to brace up to the task of uncovering cases of domestic violence, and following up such cases in the court of law, intensifying effort at awareness creation, giving prominence to the reportage of cases of domestic violence, devoting special page for discussion of domestic violence, organizing debates on the issue to enlighten the public about the incidence of violations of the rights of women and the girl-child, carrying out in-depth analyses of issues concerning domestic violence, use of improved surveillance system such as the closed circuit system installed in strategic places such as the parks, churches, markets, schools and other public places, and alerting government of any possible outbreak of violence.

The evidence from this literature review revealed media has been a useful way to expose abuse wherever it happens, and for people across the world to come and disclose information. However, researches on the contribution of media to the fights against domestic violence, have been carried from a general perspective. Although there is a large

body of research on the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, there is no known case study conducted in university of Maiduguri, faculty of social science. This leaves a gap that this study wants to fill. Therefore, this study will examine the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, a case study in the University of Maiduguri.

Theoretical Framework

It has already been established that social media is a useful media platform to creating awareness on domestic violence, and change the behaviours of the public. This is because majority of the population in the world make use of social media. Therefore, reaching the public with domestic violence education and information is possible, and can be effective in influencing their knowledge and behavior in respect to domestic violence. This forms part of the reasons why this study will adopt the agenda-setting theory as theoretical framework.

The media is known to have effects on its viewers. In fact, agenda setting theory conceptualized in 1922 by Walter Lippmann expresses that “the media shapes worldview.” (Auwalu, 2018). Agenda setting theory postulates that the media sets the public agenda by telling you what to think about, although not exactly what to think. Brynin (2004) submitted that the theory aims to determine how the media agenda affects society and why media gain so much power over people's thoughts all over the place. This theory conceptualizes and explains how important media issues are perceived in society by people and their various forces.

In order to relate the postulations and assumptions of the Agenda Setting theory to social media awareness of domestic violence, the import of this is that if domestic violence gets frequent reports in the media, it will command the attention of the audience. In doing so, social media being an avenue with millions of audiences, can be a relevant medium where attention is given to domestic violence campaigns, education, information, and reports. This is will in turn pass an information to the audience on domestic violence, knowledge of its dangers, and consequences.

Also, social media interpretation of domestic violence in the awareness campaigns, must provide action against it, prevention mechanisms, as well as ways to respond to domestic violence. In Nigeria, there have been situation where social media was used for violence campaigns that drew the attention of the public, and shape public agenda, such as the Bring Back Our Girls and My Dress My Choice.

The justification for using agenda setting theory is that since the media has the ability to influence the attitude and perception of the audience, the power to shape, filter and alter the audiences' perceptions and attitudes towards issues, the social media can bring to the attention of the audience domestic violence information and education, this will enable the audience view it as important and trigger the needed action and change.

Research Design

The research designs are the structure and strategy for obtaining a reliable and valid result of a research problem. This study will adopt the descriptive research design. Descriptive research is a research method used to determine the characteristics of a population or particular phenomenon. Descriptive research designs help researchers identify characteristics in their target population. The descriptive research is useful for this study because it is cost-effective and it allow for many types of data to be collected.

Research Method

This research will adopt a survey research method. According to Cherry (2009), a survey is a data collection tool used to gather information about individuals. This method is considered appropriate because survey is useful in the measurement of public opinion, attitudes and orientation which are dominant among a large population at a particular period (Okoro, 2001). In any research, one of the most prominent aspects of the study is the instrument chosen in order to come forth with valid results therefore the method chosen must be reliable and understandable, so that the results will be accurate.

Instrument for Data Collection

This research will use online questionnaire for data collection. The questionnaire will be design in line with the research questions and the objectives of the research, in order to get response from the respondents for interpretation. The questionnaire will be constructed in a close-ended format and written in English language to aid general

understanding and elicit accurate responses from the respondents. The advantage of this set of question is that they enable the respondents to give straight forward answers. The questionnaire will be shared by the researcher, and the reason why it will be online, is because the school session is over, and students are back home.

Population of the Study

Asika (2022) states that the population is a census of all subjects or things that have knowledge of the phenomenon under study or that contain the characteristics; subjects and elements are the individual items that make up the population. The 3,390 enrolled students of the faculty of social sciences, University of Maiduguri, 2023–2024 academic year, constitute the study's population (Exam Officer, Social Sciences, University of Maiduguri, 2023).

Sampling Technique

The need for sampling from the population is pivotal, and sampling is done in order that some elements, subjects, or respondents are taken to represent the population as a whole. This research will adopt convenience sampling in order to sample from the population. Convenience sampling is the method of selecting units from the population based on their ease of access or availability. The justification for the selection of the convenience sampling technique is due to its cost-effectiveness, and time efficiency. Convenience sampling allows for quick data collection, making it a suitable choice when seeking to gather data from readily accessible respondents.

Sample Size

The sample size according to Fagohungbe (2002), is the appropriate size that makes for better estimate of population value. For this research the sample size is 120, arrived at using convenience sampling technique, which involves selecting respondents who are easily accessible or readily available to the researcher. While convenience sampling does not follow a formula the sample size was chosen based on considerations such as time, resources, and the ease of access to respondents. In selecting the sample size, the researcher aims to ensure that it is large enough to gather meaningful data but manageable. The justification for selecting 120 respondents, is according to Busha and Harter (2023), they stated that the population can be very large or very small depending on

the size of the group of persons or subjects about which the researcher plans to make inference. Therefore, researchers can directly question only a sample (i.e., a small proportion) of the population, since the population is quite large.

Method for Data Analysis

This research will adopt the statistical method of data analysis, which collects and analyse data in order to identify and develop valuable insights. The information and data that will be gathered will be presented using statistical instruments such as tables, frequencies and percentages, and interpreted and discussed in line with the research questions and objectives. In analysing the data therefore, the responses will be tallied and arranged into frequency distribution tables, and using numbers, and percentages to quantitatively analyse the data.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

The data collected from the respondents were organised and presented in a systematic sequence. The presentation utilised tables with simple percentages, and the findings were discussed to address the research objectives and answer the research questions outlined in Chapter One of the study. A total of 120 respondents contributed to the overall sample size.

Table 1: Gender of respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	80	68%
Female	40	32%
Total	120	100%

The table above indicates that 68% PR officers who form the majority of the respondents are male, while 32% PR officers are female.

Table 2: Age of respondent

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
16 – 24	62	52%
25 – 34	56	46%
35 - above	2	2%
Total	120	100%

SOURCE: *Field survey, 2024.*

The table above shows the age of the respondents. The table indicates that 52% respondents who form the majority are within the age grade of 16-24. Others 46% are within the age grade of 25-34, while few 2% are within the age grade of 35-above.

Table 3: Role that social media plays in informing the public about the causes and consequences of domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Educate the public by raising awareness about domestic violence and its impact.	28	24%
Provides valuable information about the causes and effects of domestic violence.	44	33%
Provide a space for survivors and advocates to share stories, offer support, and build a sense of community.	12	10%
It is a powerful tool for activism, promoting changes in policy and raising voices for domestic violence survivors.	2	2%
All of the above	34	31%
Total	120	100%

The table above shows the role that social media plays in informing the public about domestic violence. It indicates that majority 33% of the respondents think social media provides valuable information about the causes and effects of domestic violence. Others 31% think social media provides all the above listed roles, valuable information about the causes and effects of domestic violence, 24%, believes that social media educates the public by raising awareness, 10% say it provides a space for survivors and advocates to share stories, offer support, and build

community, while 2% respondents think social media is a powerful tool for activism and promoting policy changes.

Table 4: Social media platforms, most effective in raising awareness about domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Facebook	34	29%
Twitter	29	24%
Instagram	12	10%
TikTok	11	9%
WhatsApp	6	5%
YouTube	4	3%
All of the above	24	20%
Total	120	100%

The table above shows the most effective social media platforms in raising awareness about domestic violence. The majority of respondents 29%, believe that Facebook is the most effective platform. Others 24% say Twitter is the most effective, 20% think that all platforms combined are the most effective, 10% said Instagram, 9% said TikTok, 5% said WhatsApp, while 3% said YouTube.

Table 5: Social media platforms assisting victims of domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Provides emotional support from others who understand their situation	24	20%
Provide victims of domestic violence with sufficient support systems	27	23%
Helps raise awareness about domestic violence and its effects	27	23%
Offers a sense of community and connection with other survivors	15	13%
All of the above	27	21%
Total	120	100%

The table above shows how social media platforms assist victims of domestic violence. Majority 23% of respondents believe that social media helps raise awareness about domestic

violence and its effects. Others 23% think social media provides victims with sufficient support systems, 21% think all of the above contribute to supporting victims, 20% say social media provides emotional support from others who understand the situation, while 13% believe social media offers a sense of community and connection with other survivors.

Table 6: How social media can be improved to better support victims of domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Provide accessible resources and hotlines for domestic violence victims	27	22%
Create safe spaces or support groups specifically for victims of domestic violence	39	33%
Improve education on how to report abuse and access help through social media	18	15%
Offer anonymous options for sharing experiences to protect the victim's identity	7	6%
All of the above	29	24%
Total	120	100%

The table above shows how social media can be improved to better support victims of domestic violence. Majority 33% of respondents believe creating safe spaces or support groups specifically for victims of domestic violence would be the most effective improvement. Others 24% think all the above would be beneficial, 22% agree on providing accessible resources and hotlines for domestic violence victims, 15% think social media should improve education on how to report abuse, while 6% suggest offering anonymous options to protect victims' identities.

Table 7: How social media campaigns can change attitudes towards domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
By increasing awareness and educating the public about domestic violence	33	26%
By providing survivors a platform to share their stories and reduce stigma	41	35%
By challenging misconceptions about victims and perpetrators	6	5%
By encouraging people to take action	5	4%
All of the above	35	30%
Total	120	100%

Source: field survey, 2024

The table above shows how social media campaigns can change attitudes towards domestic violence. The majority 35% believe that by providing survivors a platform to share their stories, social media reduces stigma. Others 30% think all of the above strategies are effective, 26%, think increasing awareness and educating the public about domestic violence can change attitudes, 5% believe that challenging misconceptions about victims and perpetrators can help, while 4% believe encouraging people to take action, can help change attitudes.

Table 8: Whether behavioural change messages on social media are effective in motivating individuals to take action against domestic violence

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	113	94%
No	7	6%
Total	120	100%

The table above shows the effectiveness of behavioural change messages on social media in motivating individuals to take action against domestic violence. Majority 94% of respondents believe that these messages are effective in motivating action, while 6% believe they are not effective. In addition, respondents suggested other ways social media and behavioural change intervention can prevent and respond to domestic violence.

According to respondents, social media and behavioural change interventions can play a significant role in preventing and responding to domestic violence by promoting awareness, challenging harmful social norms, and providing critical support. Initiatives such as social-emotional learning programs for youth and healthy relationship programs can build foundational knowledge and healthy attitudes. Social media can be used to educate the public about the dangers and consequences of domestic violence, while also encouraging people to take action, raise awareness, and promote gender equality. By creating safe spaces, such as online support groups, and amplifying survivors' voices, victims can feel empowered to speak out, share their stories, and access resources. Increasing privacy protections for victims and providing online counselling and legal resources further support their healing and safety. Behavioural change campaigns that encourage bystander intervention and challenge societal attitudes that normalise violence are crucial, as are consistent outreach efforts, legal accountability, and the involvement of influencers to spread awareness. With a combination of public education, strong support networks, and a commitment to confidentiality, social media and behavioural interventions can help create a culture of respect and reduce domestic violence.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This study is on the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, using the university of Maiduguri as a case study. In an attempt to achieve its objectives and response to raised questions, results collected in form of data were presented above in tables which are further explained below according to the research objectives.

Students' Knowledge on Social Media as a Tool for Creating Awareness on Domestic Violence

Findings show that respondents have an understanding of social media's role in creating awareness about domestic violence. Findings show that social media is viewed as a crucial tool in educating the public about the causes and consequences of domestic violence. Majority (31%) of respondents believe that social media provides valuable information about domestic violence's causes and effects. This suggests that respondents are aware of social media's potential to inform the public. Furthermore, findings support this knowledge by demonstrating which social media platforms are considered most effective in raising awareness. Majority (29%) of respondents identify Facebook as the most effective platform for awareness. These findings indicate that respondents are not only aware of social media's role but also understand which platforms are most effective in disseminating this awareness. Additionally, findings show that social media campaigns can indeed influence public attitudes toward domestic violence. Majority (35%) of respondents believe that providing survivors

with a platform to share their stories helps reduce stigma and change public perception, which highlights the awareness of respondents of the power social media campaigns have in altering societal attitudes toward domestic violence.

Social media as a Voice for Domestic Violence Victims

Social media is perceived as a powerful platform for domestic violence victims to share their experiences and find support. Majority (23%) of respondents believe social media provides sufficient support systems for victims, and raises awareness about domestic violence and its effects. These findings indicate that respondents recognise social media's capacity to offer emotional support, raise awareness, and create networks for victims to connect with others. Furthermore, the sense of community and connection with other survivors is also emphasised by (13%) respondents, suggesting that respondents understand how social media can foster solidarity among victims and create a safe space for sharing experiences. This is important because it allows victims to feel heard, reducing feelings of isolation and providing them with a sense of empowerment. In addition, findings highlight the importance of providing survivors with a platform to share their stories, as (35%) respondents agreed that this can reduce stigma, and shows that respondents perceive social media as a means of amplifying the voices of survivors and encouraging societal change.

Role of Social Media and Behavioural Change Intervention to Preventing and Responding to Domestic Violence

Findings show that respondents believe social media plays an all-encompassing role by raising awareness about domestic violence, providing valuable information, and offering a space for survivors to share their stories. This indicates that respondents see social media as a comprehensive tool for preventing domestic violence, through awareness-building and providing educational resources. Also, findings show that respondents emphasise the creation of safe spaces or support groups specifically for victims, suggesting that respondents understand the need for additional resources and support networks on social media to prevent and respond to domestic violence.

In terms of behavioural change, of respondents believe that a combination of increasing awareness, providing survivors with a platform to share their stories, and challenging misconceptions about victims and perpetrators can change attitudes toward domestic violence. This demonstrates that respondents recognise the importance of behavioural change interventions on social media in addressing domestic violence and shifting societal norms. Also, majority (94%) of respondents affirmed the effectiveness of behavioural change messages on social media in motivating individuals to take action against domestic violence. This suggests that respondents believe social media's role in spreading behavioural change messages are crucial in motivating individuals to take action, whether through intervention or supporting victims.

Conclusion

The research on the contribution of social media on public awareness of domestic violence, using the university of Maiduguri as a case study highlights the role that social media plays in addressing domestic violence. Through its capacity to raise awareness, amplify the voices of victims, and support behavioural change, social media emerges as a powerful tool in both preventing and responding to domestic violence. There is an understanding of how social media platforms, such as Facebook, can be used effectively to raise awareness and educate the public about domestic violence, the causes, effects, and consequences, due to its broad reach and accessibility. Moreover, social media is a platform for victims of domestic violence to voice their experiences, receive emotional support, and connect with others who understand their struggles. This sense of community is vital in breaking the silence surrounding domestic violence and empowering victims to take steps toward recovery and advocacy. The ability of social media to connect individuals across geographic and social boundaries fosters solidarity and reduces the isolation often felt by survivors of abuse. This connection not only allows victims to find support but also educates the broader community about the realities of domestic violence, dispelling myths and reducing stigma. The study reinforces the belief that social media can be a highly effective tool in combating domestic violence. It is not only instrumental in raising awareness but also crucial in providing support to victims and promoting the kind of behavioural change necessary to prevent domestic violence. Social media, when

strategically employed, has the capacity to influence public attitudes, empower victims, and motivate individuals to take meaningful action. By fostering a culture of awareness, support, and action, social media can significantly contribute to the prevention and response to domestic violence, ultimately helping to create safer and more supportive communities for all.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this research, the study recommends that the knowledge of students of the Department of Mass Communication, University of Maiduguri, should be enhanced on social media as a tool for creating awareness on domestic violence, specifically in courses such as online journalism.

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